

**THE AWAKENING OF NATIONAL CULTURE": UZBEK ARTISTIC GROUPS AT THE
1930 ARTS OLYMPIAD**

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the participation of Uzbek artistic groups in the First All-Union Olympiad of Theaters and Arts of the Peoples of the USSR, held in Moscow in 1930. Although previously mentioned in scholarship, the scale, significance, and impact of the Uzbek delegation have not been adequately explored. Based on a comprehensive analysis of over 60 period publications, archival documents, and visual materials, the study reconstructs the structure, repertoire, and reception of the Uzbek tour. It argues that the Olympiad served as a pivotal moment in negotiating the role of national culture within Soviet cultural policy. Uzbek artists, particularly figures like Mukhitdin Qoriyoqubov and Tamara Khanum, used this platform to assert cultural agency and formulate a distinctive interpretation of national art under Soviet conditions. The research situates this episode within broader debates on nationalism, representation, and the instrumentalization of culture during the early Stalinist period. The findings contribute to a re-evaluation of the Olympiad not as a one-time spectacle, but as a moment of cultural articulation and symbolic negotiation between the center and the periphery.

Keywords: national theater, national culture, representation, First Olympiad of the Arts of the Peoples of the USSR, Turkic, Uzbekistan

INTRODUCTION

In the late 1920s and early 1930s, during the implementation of the first five-year economic plan, the leadership of the Soviet Union faced the challenge of promoting the ideas of industrialization and collectivization, raising educational standards, and transforming attitudes toward new societal and domestic forms. One proposed solution involved engaging cultural figures in disseminating these new ideas. It was believed that borrowing forms from national culture would facilitate this effort. However, it became evident that national culture possesses inherent value and cannot be utilized purely as a technical resource without significant reinterpretation. Consequently, during the 1930s, state policies aimed to define the goals and objectives of national literature and art, resulting in a departure from the genuine national foundation.

This study aims to recontextualize a moment when artistic expression briefly negotiated space within centralized Soviet control. One vivid episode of this era was the First All-Union Olympiad of Theaters and Arts of the Peoples of the USSR, held in Moscow from June 15 to July 14, 1930. The vast delegation from Uzbekistan became not just a participant but one of the triumphant of this Olympiad.

CHAPTERS

Research Problem

Numerous analyses of Soviet "managed multiculturalism" begin with the assertion that "The Soviet Union was the world's first affirmative action empire," [1] a framing that is equally relevant in this case.

One more quotation gives us critical insight into Uzbekistan specifically, reinforcing the claim that the Olympiad should be read within the broader upheavals of cultural engineering and identity formation in the early Soviet East: "The Soviet transformation of Central Asia was a revolution not just in form, but in content — an attempt to reconfigure identity, authority, and culture from the ground up." [2]

While the participation of Uzbek artistic groups in the Olympiad is acknowledged, existing descriptions lack empirical detail, leaving critical aspects underexplored. For instance, it is mentioned in an article by Mukhabbat Tulyakhodjaeva that investigates the relevance of the international development of theatrical cultures in terms of the contemporary state of the art of Uzbekistan. Participation in the Olympiad is described briefly, with a citation from a single source, *Sovetskii teatr* magazine (*Soviet theatre*). It has been noted that two theater ensembles participated: the Khamza Theater and the State Uzbek Musical Theater. However, no mention is made of the numerous concerts performed by the musical ensemble and the national orchestra. It is rightly pointed out that this tour marked the beginning of an exchange of creative experiences among theatrical artists [3]. It is not noted, however, that representatives of the national republics not only demonstrated their ability to gain symbolic capital but also shared it with the state.

Initially conceived as the beginning of a regular showcase of Soviet national policy achievements, the Olympiad ultimately remained a one-time occurrence. Moreover, it was nearly erased from official history and relegated to archival obscurity. A century later, it demands reconsideration.

This paper fills existing gaps and investigates the specifics of the touring trip undertaken by the delegation from Uzbekistan.

Approach

The primary methods employed were archival analysis and discourse analysis. The dataset consists of more than 60 publications across various sources:

- Federal general-interest newspapers such as *Izvestia*, *Pravda*, *Trud*, *Komsomolskaya Pravda*, and *Gudok*.
- Local newspapers such as *Vechernyaya Moskva*, *Rabochaya Moskva*, *O'zbekiston Ovozi*, *Zarya Vostoka*.
- Specialized journals and newspapers including *Rabis*, *Ekran*, *Sovetsky Teatr*, *Tsirk i Estrada*, *Literaturnaya Gazeta*, *Rabochy i Teatr*, *Revolyutsiya i Natsionalnosti*.
- Additionally, one article is included from publications distributed abroad by the USSR, including *Soviet Union Review* in English and *V.O.K.S* in French.

Furthermore, four newsreel films have been preserved, including one sound film.

In the local press, only two short notes are known in the newspaper *O'zbekiston Ovozi* (*Voice of Uzbekistan*), which do not reflect the success that the delegation had in Moscow.

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Main Provisions and Findings

Context. A century ago, the leadership of the Soviet Union sought to teach society new forms of communication, new skills, and to cultivate new literature and culture. At the same time, Stalin and the party feared the growing independence of the national republics and fought against what they called nationalism, although very often it was simply originality and independence of judgment.

This period was marked by debates over national culture, as well as suspicions and allegations of nationalism. Central Asia was regarded as a potentially problematic region, along with the Caucasus, Ukraine, and Belarus, to name a few. National culture was understood ambiguously—as an innovation that could facilitate a breakthrough in propaganda—but there was no real foundation for this [4].

Accusations of nationalism filled the pages of newspapers and magazines and also were repeatedly heard at the XVI Congress of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks), which was held simultaneously with the Olympiad.

The leaders of the USSR, delegates of the Congress, foreign journalists, and heads of departments of culture and education were able to personally encounter the entire diversity of multinational culture at the Olympiad.

The Olympiad demonstrated that national art remained a space of freedom. It indicated that the party had to control the artists' activities more strictly. This process would lead to the emergence of the concept of socialist realism in the mid-1930s. It was a theoretical concept that did not correspond to reality. Socialist realism was supposed to be a multinational culture, but multinational only in language and external forms. In essence, the all-Union proletarian culture was required to be not national, but supranational.

Many outstanding figures could not be controlled. Later, hundreds of Olympiad participants, including directors, leading actors, and playwrights, were repressed. In the first wave of terror, playwright Gulyam Zafari, the author of "Khalima", was imprisoned. The First National Singer Mukhitdin Qoriyoqubov (Kari-Yakubov in Russian media) was repressed in the last wave. In 1947, he was convicted.

Turkic delegations at Olympiad. The event brought together dozens of artistic groups and approximately a thousand participants from across the Soviet Union. The delegation from Uzbekistan was one of the most numerous.

One of the organizers named the event the "Olympiad of the East," though it could just as well be described as an Olympiad of Soviet Turkic art. In addition to Uzbekistan, delegations from Azerbaijan, Bashkiria, Tatarstan, Turkmenistan were participated. On the occasion of the Congress of the Communist Party, representatives from Turkey [5] were also present in Moscow. They are mentioned in a single note in the context of the Olympiad, but there is no precise confirmation of their attendance at the performances. The high probability of such attendance is supported by the fact that the main organizer of the Olympiad, playwright A. Glebov, had previously worked in Turkey as part of a diplomatic mission. In any case, the task of examining the Olympiad as a space for cultural diplomacy interaction exclusively among Turkic peoples remains relevant for future research.

The tour. The delegation from Uzbekistan was numerous. It included a drama theater, a musical theater, an instrumental ensemble, and a dance group.

The visit to Moscow was part of a large-scale tour. In May, part of the delegation visited Kazan, after the Olympiad went to Leningrad, and planned to visit Rostov-on-Don, Makhachkala, Tbilisi, and Baku.

These were very well-organized tours. A special brochure was prepared with a circulation of 3,000 copies, containing a brief summary of the performances, a script of the concert program, a historical overview, and photographs of the troupe.

Only three plays were presented at the Olympiad several times: "Khalima", "Khudjum" (the title of the play was translated as "Offensive Against the Chador"/"Наступление на чадру"), and "Вредители хлопка/Vrediteli khlopka" ("The Cotton Destroyers"). But as part of the tour, the performances "Ikki Kommunist" ("Two Communists"), "Фархад и Ширин" ("Farhad and Shirin"), "Мятеж" ("Rebellion"), and "Уртақляр"/"О'ртоқлар" ("Comrade") were repeatedly staged.

As part of the Olympiad's film program, the *Uzbekgoskino* film "Последний бек" (*The Last Bek*) was screened. Additionally, at the same time, the film "Прокаженная" (*The Leper Woman*) was being shown in cinemas. In addition to the plays, concert programs were prepared.

In dramatic performances, critics noted an excessive aestheticization, a "Turandot-like" style [6] (originating from the fact that Uzbek actors were trained by masters of the Vakhtangov Theater), and a lack of originality. However, the Olympiad jury refused to judge the dramatic theater too strict, instead expressing strong approval of its activities. The musical theater received even greater support, with

special recognition given to Qoriyoqubov and his valuable contributions. Naturally, the assessment was influenced by the fact that the theater operated in a complex region plagued by ongoing conflicts, where just a year earlier, the legendary Khamza, a close associate of Qoriyoqubov, had been killed.

Quantitatively, more publications were dedicated to the concert program and musical performances. Traditional music and dances, in which national forms were preserved, were analyzed in detail. At the same time, there was a mixed reception of the stage act set to the *Budyonny March*, which was dedicated to the recent Sino-Soviet conflict of 1929 over the Chinese Eastern Railway. Some critics welcomed the revolutionary theme [7], while others were dissatisfied with the form, executed in the agitprop theatre *Sinyaya Bluza (The Blue Blouse)* style [8].

We do not know the exact number of performances, but many of them certainly took place in open areas, worker clubs, and factories.

For example, one of the events was a joint tea gathering of Uzbek artists and the choir of the Yerevan Conservatory with workers from the *Krasnaya Zarya* textile factory [9]. The event took place outdoors in Fili Park, with more than 500 participants. Thus, the interaction between artists and the audience was not merely a representation of cultural products but rather a more complex form of engagement. National culture and its natives became an integral part of everyday life for the Moscow workers.

Perception. The Olympiad was actively covered in the press, sound newsreels were filmed, and audio programs were broadcast on the radio. In unpublished memoirs [10], there is an episode describing how the musicians from the ensemble saw themselves on a sound newsreel [11] for the first time in their lives. The clash of traditional art and new technologies frightened, but also interested.

It is interesting to note how the participation of Uzbek artists was covered by local, federal, and international media.

In Uzbek. The first article in newspaper *O'zbekiston Ovozi*, dated June 11 [12], reports on the arrival and reception of the delegation at Kazansky Railway Station by officials. Already at this stage, social and political aspects emerge as more significant than cultural ones. A noteworthy aspect is the second article dated June 19 [13]. It was published while the Olympiad was still ongoing, yet it seems to summarize the outcomes and creates a myth of Uzbekistan's success rather than describing real achievements. Interestingly, in an effort to lend credibility, the author of the article engages in name-dropping, mentioning notable figures who, in reality, had no connection to the Olympiad. Alongside actual officials (A. Lunacharsky, Ex-Head of Narkompros/People's Commissariat for Education, F. Kon, Head of Glaviskusstvo, T. Ryskulov, member of Council of People's Commissars of the Soviet Union, O. Litovsky, chairman of Glavrepertkom, a commission for approval of performers' repertoires), the names of the famous German revolutionary playwright Ernst Toller and the legendary writer Maxim Gorky appear. However, neither of them visited Moscow in 1930.

In Russian. Mentions of Uzbek artists are more common than of any other participants, excluding the Georgian Rustaveli Theater, the main triumphant of the showcase. At the moment, more than 60 pieces of content are known, including short notes and large articles about music. Dancer Tamara Khanum became the only artist to whom a personal article was dedicated [14]. National music and the musical ensemble are also frequently noted in numerous publications.

Among the Turkic participants, the delegation Uzbek stood out as the most prominent and widely discussed. Its leaders, Mukhitdin Qoriyoqubov and Tamara Khanum, received enthusiastic acclaim in the press. While some reporters criticized an overemphasis on ethnographic form, these critiques did not escalate into accusations of nationalism. Within this context, Uzbek artists formulated their own response to the complex question of national culture—a response that remains insufficiently analyzed.

In English. It is noteworthy that in the magazine *Soviet Union Review*, which was published in the USA, in the article "Art Olympiad Awards", only one photo was placed, and it depicts an Uzbek musical group. In this article we can find the text from jury conclusion: "This theater, in the opinion of

the jury represented a very gratifying sign of the awakening of Uzbek national culture" [15]. This piece of content confirms that cultural expression, including national dance, music, and costume, became tools in Soviet efforts to impress foreign audiences with the USSR's cultural diversity and unity "The Soviet Union used national cultures as part of its international performance of socialist modernity—projecting an image of a harmonious, progressive multiethnic state to the world." [16]

DISCUSSION

Interpretation of Findings

This study reframes our understanding of the participation of Uzbek artistic groups in the 1930 Olympiad by showing that it was more extensive, diverse, and significant than previously described, signaling a key intersection between national cultural expression and Soviet ideological frameworks. While Uzbek artists gained symbolic capital, their agency was shaped by the broader mechanisms of cultural engineering under Stalinist oversight. The Olympiad functioned as a site where Soviet center-periphery relations played out in practice, legitimizing national cultural forms while simultaneously constraining their independent development.

Notably, our findings suggest that national culture was understood as both a celebrated expression and a carefully managed ideological tool—serving the Soviet Union's effort to project unity, diversity, and revolutionary transformation at home and abroad. The case of Qoriyoqubov and Tamara Khanum exemplifies how national artists were central to this process, negotiating visibility, recognition, and ideological conformity within the framework of Soviet identity politics.

Future Research Directions

Building on the findings of this paper, several directions emerge for further scholarly investigation:

- Exploring Uzbek archival materials to access lesser-known official records, correspondence, and internal theater reports.
- Oral history documentation—interviewing descendants and regional historians to uncover artist experiences beyond Soviet state narratives.
- Comparative analysis—contrasting Uzbek participation with other Turkic delegations (Azerbaijan, Tatarstan, Bashkiria) to assess cultural policy patterns across the Soviet Union.

Investigating these aspects will shed light on how the Olympiad shaped cultural production, self-representation, and ideological constraints for national republics not only in Moscow but also upon their return to Uzbekistan.

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